

DL Diffusion MRI enhancing may lead to incorrect diagnosis

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Introduction

Diffusion MRI (dMRI) measures diffusion in tissues by sampling q-space to build a propagator function. A dense sampling exam would be desirable but it is unbearable in practice. Hence, Deep Learning (DL) techniques are applied for mimicking results from denser samplings. We will test if diagnostic information is maintained with DL.

Methods

Experiments were made for obtaining equivalent versions of images, augmenting b-value from 1000 to 2000 or number of gradient directions from 21 to 61. Same methodology applied, using a DL architecture [1] which extracts features from the mixture of inputs. Image quality metrics were computed between output and ground truth and hypothesis test was computed between all sorts of images and JHU-Atlas [2].

Results

SSIM above .95 for both experiments on every set. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for first experiment's Mann-Whitney test differencing controls from patients are (Real/Synthetic) 9/5 RTAP, 17/5 RTOP, 8/9 RTPP. For second, t-test differencing chronic and episodic migraine are (21/61/Synthetic) 5/5/0 FA, 3/10/1 AD, 7/14/0 MD.

a) SSIM distribution of RTAP, RTOP and RTPP computed over controls between real B=2000 data and synthetic B=2000 data. b) SSIM distribution of FA, AD and MD between real 61 gradients data and 61 gradients synthetic data. c) Comparison between images of B=1000 real gradients,

B=2000 real gradients and B=2000 synthetic for RTAP, RTOP and RTPP. d) Comparison between images of 21 real gradients, 61 real gradients and 61 synthetic gradients for FA, AD and MD.

Discussion & conclusion

Results suggest that averaging procedures blur significant differences between both controls and patients and patients of different kinds of disease until almost completely vanish. For splitting methodology from results, an ongoing challenge [3] has been set to maintain significant differences while enhancing visual quality using the same training data from the second experiment.

References

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